

A tool for the data notarization with the Blockchain to ensure security and privacy

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Abstract— This paper presents a trustworthy blockchain-based framework designed to ensure secure, immutable, and pseudo-anonymized data collection at field level. It outlines the context in which the framework is being conceived and developed, beginning with an analysis of the state of the art in Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) and Blockchain, with a particular focus on their potential applications in data management. Special attention is given to the FIWARE ecosystem, as the ultimate goal is to develop a data-gathering tool functioning as an extension of the FIWARE Context Broker.

The core of the solution consists of two smart contracts that implement the Proof of Existence (PoE) and the Real-Time Monitoring Data Notarization (RT-MDN) mechanisms. These contracts respectively handle the certification of individual documents and batches of monitoring data, the latter representing the most innovative aspect of the work due to its periodic production requirements.

A first Proof of Concept (PoC) will be developed, and preliminary results will be presented. The work is being carried out within the EU co-funded “DigiBUILD” project.

Keywords—Blockchain, notarization, data certification, FIWARE, Proof-of-Existence

I. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we introduce a tool that enables “data notarization,” namely the certification of a document or dataset through the computation of a cryptographic footprint and its storage on a Blockchain. The Blockchain acts as a distributed ledger that inherently guarantees the integrity and immutability of the information it contains. The footprint (i.e., the digest of an asymmetric cryptographic function) is used to address two key requirements:

- Minimizing the amount of data stored on the Blockchain, as storage is the main cost driver.
- Preserving the privacy of the original data, given that information recorded on the Blockchain is publicly accessible.

For this reason, all the potentially sensitive raw data remain off-chain (e.g., in a time-series database, TSDB), while only their hash is notarized on the Blockchain. By applying the same cryptographic function at any later time, the authenticity and integrity of the data can be verified, provided that the resulting hash matches the one permanently stored on-chain.

From an implementation perspective, the proposed information-sharing infrastructure extends the FIWARE Context Broker [1]. Both Orion v2 and Orion-LD are supported through a customized MongoDB backend enabling long-term persistence of raw data. In the current prototype, Context Broker data (NGSI entities) are notarized on an Ethereum-based public testnet (Görlı). This is achieved via the FIWARE subscription mechanism, following the application of the KECCAK256 (SHA3) hashing algorithm—the winner of the SHA3 Cryptographic Hash Algorithm [2].

II. STATE OF THE ART

A. DLT and Blockchain

Since the birth of Web 1.0 in 1991 with Tim Berners Lee, the World Wide Web has undergone several evolutions. With the transition from Web 1.0 to Web 2.0 in 2005, there has been a shift from a unidirectional Web in which actors can be categorized into producer and consumer to a participative Web in which consumers can also produce content, especially with the emergence of social networks, forums, and blogs.

The evolution of the Web continues in two coexisting directions, the first one is the semantic web [3] with RDF OWL and SPARQL. The other is the so-called Web3, a term coined by Ethereum co-founder Gavin Wood in 2014 and encompassing all digital innovations and applications on the Internet that are based on Blockchain technology. With Web3, in fact, it aims to achieve a new World Wide Web that is decentralized, permissionless, with native payments, and that is trustless.

As reported in [4], the blockchain is part of distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) which allows a distributed ledger to be stored and updated in a decentralized manner. The Blockchain is a P2P DLT structured as a chain of blocks in which cryptography enables secure data transmission and immutability of records, in a decentralized environment.

Web3 applications can be divided into 4 layers, the first of which, layer 0, is the hardware and infrastructure layer and includes the Internet, network adapters such as WLAN, LAN, Ethernets and nodes, and real connection protocols such as TCP/IP, RPC, WebSocket. The subsequent layers are shown in the Fig. 1. Layer 1 encapsulates the core technologies of major blockchain networks, among them we find hashing algorithms as well as consensus mechanisms such as Proof of Work (PoW), Proof of Stake (PoS) and Proof of Authority (PoA).

Layer 2 provides the technologies with the purpose of improving in terms of scalability and adding the functionality of blockchain networks.

The last layer contains all the services that simplify the access and use of Blockchains such as DEXs and wallet providers.

The Blockchain can be divided into two major classes. The permissionless and the permissioned Blockchains. The main difference between these two types of Blockchains lies in the fact that while in the permissionless any entity can decide to participate with its own computers in the network, in the permissioned Blockchain restrictions are applied to be part of it and to the control procedures.

As reported in [5] the two types of Blockchain have distinctions mainly in two features.

- **Trustlessness and immutability:** while in a permissionless Blockchain, there is no need for a central authority and the network is immutable, in permissioned networks transactions could be rolled back by a centralized agency.
- **Distributed Consensus and Transparency:** while in a permissionless Blockchain, each participant maintains a copy of the entire network, in permissioned networks copies may not be shared with all participants but some participants may have only part of the copy.

Fig. 1. The Web3 landscape layers.

B. Proof of Work, proof of Stake, proof of Authority

In Blockchains, in a distributed environment, the problem of consensus emerges. In distributed environments, there is no central authority, so it is the network nodes themselves that control the network, authorizing, or denying activities within it. Therefore, the need arises to have consensus methods among the network nodes. Based on the different needs specific to the types of blockchain, different consensus methods arise. There are many different types of consensus mechanisms as reported in [6], among them the most commonly used ones are the Proof of Work (PoW), the Proof of Stake (PoS) and the Proof of Authority (PoA).

The PoW was introduced with the Bitcoin Blockchain [7]. In PoW, users are required to complete complex computational calculations before submitting new transactions into the network. PoS, on the other hand, differs from PoW in the selection of participants in mining activities. Anyone with even a small amount of cryptocurrency can participate in network activity. The activities that can be carried out by users of the network are many among them is the possibility of delegating part of one's cryptocurrency to other participants and sharing the reward.

Finally, in PoA the set of validators consists of a group of approved accounts. The strength of PoA lies in the fact that individuals who have earned the right to be approved are incentivized to maintain a good reputation within the network. These reasons make this approach appropriate for private consortiums.

C. Ethereum and Hyperledger

One of the most popular Blockchains, along with Bitcoin, is Ethereum [8]. Ethereum overcomes many of bitcoin's own limitations, the first being the scripting language, which, unlike Bitcoin, supports full Turing-completeness. It also implements an additional abstract layer that allows users to create their own rules on transitions using smart contracts [9].

Ethereum is a decentralized, public Blockchain network that was created to enable smart contracts. The key points of Ethereum are:

- Immutability: once a transaction is recorded it cannot be altered or deleted.
- Proof of corruption: all smart contracts are executed automatically and cannot be altered by any single entity.
- Security: Ethereum utilizes a consensus algorithm PoW/PoS.
- No downtime: even if one node goes offline, the network will continue to operate thanks to the decentralized nature of Ethereum. The gas, also, ensures that the network is not congested by spam transactions and Dapps.

Ether, in the case of B2B applications, also different features of the blockchain may be useful. Hyperledger enables people to build solutions using distributed ledger technology. Hyperledger technology provides different and interesting features, especially in the case of B2B applications. These are, for example, restrictions to network participation, the possibility of defining own coins and different types of consensus mechanisms. Table 1 shows the main differences between the features of Ethereum and Hyperledger.

TABLE I. ETHEREUM/HYPERLEDGER FEATURES

Features	Ethereum	Hyperledger
Confidentiality	Public Blockchain	Private Blockchain
Purpose	Client-side B2C applications	Enterprise-level B2B applications
Governance	Ethereum Developers	Linux Foundation
Participation	Anyone	Organizations having Certificate of Authorization
Programming language	Solidity	Golang, JavaScript, or Java
Consensus mechanism	POW/PoS-Mechanism	Pluggable consensus mechanism
Speed	Less	More
Cryptocurrency	Ether	None

To take advantage of the capabilities offered by both technologies, especially in the case of Ethereum-based enterprise projects, Hyperledger Besu, an open source Ethereum client, was designed. It can be run on the Ethereum public network or on private permissioned networks. Besu includes several consensus algorithms including PoS, PoW, PoA, IBFT, CLIQUE and has comprehensive permissioning schemes designed specifically for uses in a consortium environment.

The main features of Hyperledger Besu are:

- The Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM): allows the deployment and execution of smart contracts.
- Consensus Algorithms: Hyperledger Besu implements PoS, PoA and PoW consensus algorithms.
- Storage: using a RocksDB key-value database to persist chain data locally.
- P2P networking: implements Ethereum's devp2p network protocols and an additional sub-protocol for IBF2.
- User-facing APIs: provides main net Ethereum, EEa JSON-RPC APIs and GraphQL API.
- Monitoring: allows you to monitor node and network performance.
- Privacy: the transactions could be kept private between the involved parties.
- Permissioning: a permissioned network allows only specified nodes and accounts to participate.

The use of blockchain is becoming increasingly important in several areas, one example being the possibility of using it in the Physical Internet (PI), an open global logistics system that increases the efficiency and sustainability of freight transportation [10]. This paper shows the possible applications of blockchain in PI and compares Hyperledger Fabric and Hyperledger Besu.

III. FIWARE AND BLOCKCHAIN EXPLOITATION

A. Smart contracts

One of the most interesting possibilities offered by distributed ledgers (e.g., Blockchains) is to be able to initiate on them the smart contracts, codes built to perform tasks when certain conditions are met. As codes that can be run on blockchains, smart contracts allow contracts to be managed between parties without the need for a third party.

Smart contracts eliminate the potential for human error and can automate tasks that would normally require human involvement because they are executed by code instead of people.

One of the benefits of runs them on the blockchain is that it is a decentralized system that exists between all authorized parties, eliminating the need for intermediaries and saving time and conflict. Although blockchain technology is undoubtedly faster, cheaper, and more secure than traditional systems. As a result, we are witnessing an increase in the execution of smart contracts on various blockchain networks such as Ethereum, Solana, Tezos, and Hyperledger.

The growing popularity of decentralized applications has led to a considerable increase in recent years in the development of smart contracts and their application in different areas, whether Decentralized finance (DeFi) applications, Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs), Government, Internet of Things (IoT), etc.

In [11] the authors report an in-depth study of the combination of blockchain and IoT showing how smart contracts enable the automation of complex processes that, at the same time, become verifiable with significant reductions in cost and time.

B. The FIWARE platform

FIWARE [12] is an open-source platform made of easy-to-use components, called Generic Enablers (GE), that can be assembled together and with other third-party components so as to create quick and cost-effective applications and services to accelerate the development of Smart Solutions, Digital Twins, and Data Spaces in a wide variety of domains of digital transformation.

The only mandatory component of any “Powered by FIWARE” solution is the FIWARE Context Broker GE, which provides all the functionalities for managing the entire lifecycle of context information including updates, queries, registrations and subscriptions. The Context Broker may store data in the short to medium term using a data store. FIWARE promotes a standard, called Next Generation Service Interface (NGSI) protocol [13], that describes how to collect, manage, and publish context information, and additionally adds certain elements that allow exploiting collected data. FIWARE NGSI is the application programming interface (API) exported by a FIWARE Context Broker. The FIWARE NGSI API defines:

- A data model for context information, which is based on a simple information model using the notion of context entities (representing a thing, i.e., any physical or logical object) and their attributes and related metadata.
- A context data interface for exchanging information by means of query, subscription, and update operations.
- a context availability interface for exchanging information on how to obtain context information.

FIWARE NGSI API specifications have evolved over time, initially matching NGSI-v2 specifications, now aligning with the ETSI NGSI-Linked Data (LD) standard [14]. NGSI-LD formalizes the structure of context entities to a greater degree by restricting data attributes to be defined as either Property attributes or Relationship attributes only.

Orion is an implementation of the Publish/Subscribe Context Broker GE and offers access to it via NGSI Representational State Transfer (REST) API [15]. As shown in Fig. 5, Orion foresees a set of operations the context producers generate and update context information that are provided to context consumers. Context consumption can be carried out by means of synchronous or asynchronous tasks.

Fig. 2. Orion Context Broker GE operations [16].

Orion has evolved with NGSI-v2 and then NGSI-LD. The Orion-LD Context Broker GE is a NGSI-LD Broker, which supports the NGSI-LD and the NGSIv2 APIs. Alternatives to Orion Context Broker are Stellio Context Broker GE and Scorpio Broker GE, which can also be used in federated environments.

Numerous open-source FIWARE Generic Enablers have been implemented, built around the FIWARE Context Broker, dealing with interfacing with the Internet of Things (IoT), robots and third-party systems, security, monetization, analysis and visualization of context information for making smart decisions, etc. In Fig. 3, the main GEs in the FIWARE catalogue are presented.

Fig. 3. FIWARE Catalogue [13].

FIWARE can provide interoperability among systems, although no reliability is provided for data exchange. Blockchain technology could fulfil such a gap by providing secure and reliable data exchange.

C. Blockchain enabled use-cases

This section briefly introduces the main use cases for the exploitation of the Blockchain, in particular in the context of data management, as schematically reported in Fig. 4.

The DLT and Blockchain technology can provide a single source of data truth for the data-driven application, as one trusted and distributed system of recording information. Data coming from different heterogeneous data sources can be collected and registered into a distributed blockchain ledger, allowing the distributed applications to read and optionally write this trusted shared storage system and leverage the information validated by the technology itself.

When multiple stakeholders are involved (i.e. different applications, business units, or even corporate entities), a distributed blockchain allows credentials-based access management for secure collaboration on the shared trusted distributed data storage. If data we can be trusted and verified at its operational layer, data pipelines can be built to its relevant consumers without frictions.

In general, concerning data management and exchange, the main use cases which can beneficially exploit Blockchain and smart contracts can be categorized as it follows:

- **Economic Transaction:** Blockchain Smart contracts for payments between two (or more) actors. Token as digital representation of a value for assets, used to reward (or penalize) users. (e.g., incentivization of actors involved in DR programs according to their behaviour).
- **Process Control:** Blockchain smart contracts used to manage inter-processes activities (e.g., the control DR flexibility services and energy transactions, thanks to the application of smart contracts to prosumers' flexibility aggregation and local peer-to-peer energy trading, making the transactions trackable and tamper-proof).
- **Data Management:** Blockchain Hybrid approaches for data storage minimize the costs and assure the necessary scaling up. Distributed databases and off-chain approached used to improve the storage capabilities without losing the advantages provided by a distributed system.
- **Notarization - Hashing timestamped occurrences of files and/or data on public blockchain notarizes them immutably.**
- **Interoperability:** Interledger Protocols used to reduce the entry barrier for new players, leading to a more competitive environment of products and services. Integration with any type of ledger with a variety of higher-level protocols, maintaining the advantages provided by the distributed ledgers of transparency, security and trust.

Fig. 4. Blockchain use cases.

In this work, we are focussing on the Notarization, to provide the needed level of security and reliability of the data exchanged.

IV. THE SECURITY AND PRIVACY LAYER

The Security and Privacy Layer tool is mainly composed by two components, as depicted in the figure below:

- The Proof of Existence (PoE) Certification
- The Real Time Monitoring (RTM) Data Certification

Fig. 5. Software architecture and data flow.

The two components allow the connection to the underlying Blockchain: the main difference is basically the periodicity of their call and the smart contract implementing the related functionalities. Conceptually, they both implement “data notarization”. The PoE is applied to single documents, such as an energetic certification document or a configuration file, and is used from time to time, with no periodicity. The notarization of RTM data is a bit more complex, since it is applied periodically to monitoring data. In this case, to avoid overwhelming the Blockchain with transactions at the same (typically high) rate of the sensor production – which is generally not sustainable for most types of Blockchain – monitoring data are periodically retrieved by the tool from the external off-chain storage. The hash is then calculated over a bulk of data of the same time interval, and notarized. In the current version of the prototype running in lab, 15 minutes has emerged as a good trade-off between granularity and efficiency of Blockchain usage: every 15 minutes sharp (i.e., at HH:00:00, HH:15:00, HH:30:00, and HH:45:00) monitoring data collected in the last 15 minutes interval are retrieved and sorted from an experimental InfluxDB. The SHA3 algorithm is applied, and the resulting hash notarized into the Ethereum-based testnet.

The two components, PoE and RTM, will have specific smart contracts optimised for the two different cases. RTM and PoE represent the two software components developed inside the Security and Privacy Layer, with the associated smart contracts, Monitoring Data Notarization (MDN) and the homonym Proof-of-Existence (PoE) contract. The two components include the FIWARE Context Broker, used for subscription and notification of the harmonized data, in terms of NGSI Entities. An

InfluxDB is included as default TSDB, if no external storage is available for the monitoring data. As for the PoE, an external program is supposed to exist, to provide it with the documents to be notarized, as defined by the user of the tool.

V. PROOF OF CONCEPT

A. Description of the RTM-based application

This PoC was developed in order to produce something capable of retrieving data from a database, divide them into 15 minutes sharp blocks and notarize them using the tool we are describing.

The rationale underneath this application is the following: the core of the application is the query that produces data with the timestamp rounded to the nearest 15 minutes sharp. This query is written in SQL and before writing it in our API it was tested using Azure Data Studio.

Fig. 6. Architecture of the API.

We may have two types of data coming from this API: historic data and real time data. Historic data are the output of the query of the server, they are static and not modifiable. The structure of the data is the following:

```
67.93000030517578,2023-02-03 13:15:24,A2MQTT/W4/Power_P_1_7_0/Cv
```

Fig. 7. Original data type.

The first element is the actual data coming from the sensor, associated with the date and time and finally the name of the type of power registered from the specific sensor. Those types of data get downloaded from the sensor through an MQTT broker, and this is exactly the second type of data that we can download from the API. Connecting the API to real time MQTT Broker would allow us to download batches of 15 minutes data and send them to the application. The API will allow two methods: an HTTP GET Request and an HTTP POST Request from two different endpoints. The GET Request will retrieve the data, while the POST Request is intended to write the obtained data appropriately modified to the notarization tool. The retrieved data are slightly different from the original ones: to preserve the original date, we developed a simple timestamp calculator that outputs the timestamp of the quarter of hour in object, but without modifying the original date and time.

```

,DateTime,TagName,Value,casted_timestamp
0,2022-06-29 12:24:55.000000,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh,-17.15999984741211,1656497700
1,2022-06-29 12:24:53.4110000,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh,0.0,1656497700
2,2022-06-29 12:24:56.1790000,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh,0.0,1656497700
3,2022-07-19 11:00:43.0500000,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh,-17.15999984741211,1658221200
4,2022-07-19 11:00:41.9620000,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh,0.0,1658221200
5,2022-07-21 09:29:54.0630000,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh,17.10300064086914,1658387700
6,2022-07-21 10:22:24.6390000,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh,-17.15999984741211,1658391300
7,2022-07-21 10:22:23.3300000,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh,0.0,1658391300
8,2022-07-21 10:22:26.6660000,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh,0.0,1658391300
9,2022-09-27 15:53:19.9910000,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh,0.0,1664286300
  
```

Fig. 8. Processed data.

You can clearly see from Figure 3 that the only thing that recalls the quarter of hour subdivision is the timestamp, all the other data are preserved as they are in the database.

The API will also be able to register the requests it receives, and those requests will be available at a third endpoint that returns the IP that requested the connection, the date and time, and the query.

B. Demonstration

To connect to the SQL Server, we define a connection string, check the validity of the connection and execute the query to download all the available data for a given TagName with the date and time rounded to the nearest quarter of hour. The rounding is done directly by the query that will return two types of Date columns, one rounded and one not. The rounded column will be eventually transformed into a UNIX timestamp, in order to simplify the following phase. The timestamp is used to divide the obtained results into batches with the same date, and this will be the outcome of the API, appropriately serialized. The data will be available to be posted in the form of a .json file containing as a key a string with the timestamp and the TagName and as a value a dictionary of all the registered values for that specific quarter of hour.

```

1  {
2  "1656497700,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh": {
3      "2022-06-29 12:24:53.4110000": 0.0,
4      "2022-06-29 12:24:55.0000000": -17.15999984741211,
5      "2022-06-29 12:24:56.1790000": 0.0
6  },
7  "1658221200,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh": {
8      "2022-07-19 11:00:41.9620000": 0.0,
9      "2022-07-19 11:00:43.0500000": -17.15999984741211
10 },
11 "1658387700,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh": {
12     "2022-07-21 09:29:54.0630000": 17.10300064086914
13 },
14 "1658391300,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh": {
15     "2022-07-21 10:22:23.3300000": 0.0,
16     "2022-07-21 10:22:24.6390000": -17.15999984741211,
17     "2022-07-21 10:22:26.6660000": 0.0
18 },
19 "1664286300,Energy_Ameno_2_8_0_BBB6020.Wh": {
20     "2022-09-27 15:53:19.9910000": 0.0
21 }

```

Fig. 9. The output of a POST request to the API. Those package are the ones that will be notarized, using the timestamp as a reference.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented a blockchain-based solution designed to provide decentralized security and privacy. We also reviewed the state of the art and reported the initial results. The tool is built around two smart contracts—one for PoE and one for RT-MDN—each operating with its own data-certification periodicity.

This data-notarization mechanism enables several real-world applications. For instance, it can ensure non-repudiation in data-trading scenarios: buyers can verify the authenticity of the data they purchase, while sellers are protected from disputes regarding the validity of the data they provide. Another straightforward use case concerns long-term data integrity: notarization makes it possible to preserve data over time and to detect any degradation or loss.

As a next step, a complete Proof of Concept will be developed as a fully “Powered by FIWARE” application, paving the way for the first prototype ready for real-world deployment..

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